

Discrete magnification lens model: A new hybrid multi-scale modelling method for fluid-particle systems

Behrad Esgandari^{*}, Daniel Queteschiner, Stefan Pirker, Simon Schneiderbauer^{*}

Department of Particulate Flow Modelling, Johannes Kepler University, Altenbergerstr. 69, 4040 Linz, Austria

HIGHLIGHTS

- A novel hybrid multi-scale model by concurrently coupling TFM and CFD-DEM.
- Speedup balance versus accuracy by leveraging the benefits of both TFM and CFD-DEM.
- The DML corrects the non-physical behavior of TFM in crossing jets problem.
- The DML is capable of reproducing the particle clusters in unbounded fluidization.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Hybrid multi-scale modelling
Two-fluid model
CFD-DEM
Fluid-particle flows
Particle-trajectory crossing
Unbounded fluidization

ABSTRACT

We present a novel hybrid multi-scale model, referred to as “discrete magnification lens” method, which utilizes a computational fluid dynamics coupled to discrete element method (CFD-DEM) approach within a specific region of interest in a two-fluid model (TFM) simulation. We applied the discrete magnification lens to the crossing jet problem, where the TFM fails due to lack of considering bi-modal velocity distribution in its formulation. It was observed that adopting the discrete magnification lens, can effectively alter the non-physical behavior of the TFM to obey the behavior seen from CFD-DEM simulations. Moreover, the ability of the discrete magnification lens in reproducing particle clusters and improving the TFM predictions in case of unbounded fluidization simulations was further shown. We found that the discrete magnification lens can effectively enhance the TFM predictions in a complex fluid-particle system while requiring less numerical costs compared to the full-scale CFD-DEM simulations.

1. Introduction

Fluid-particle flows (i.e., particle-laden flows) are common in environmental flows such as sediment transport and volcanic eruption, and many engineering applications, including, pneumatic conveying,

fluidized beds, spouted beds and risers. The presence of a dispersed phase (particle phase) gives rise to a broad range of length and time scales that needs to be considered in the modelling of such flows. In addition, the large separation of scales observed in particle laden flows, wherein processes happen at the microscale affecting the structures at

^{*} Corresponding authors at: Department of Particulate Flow Modelling, Johannes Kepler University, Altenbergerstr. 69, 4040 Linz, Austria.

E-mail addresses: behrad.esgandari@jku.at (B. Esgandari), simon.schneiderbauer@jku.at (S. Schneiderbauer).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2024.120094>

Received 7 May 2024; Received in revised form 8 July 2024; Accepted 15 July 2024

Available online 20 July 2024

0032-5910/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

the macroscale, poses a challenge to the modelling of these flows [1]. Therefore, a multi-scale modelling strategy which can model fluid-particle flows at different time and length scales with different levels of detail is needed [2].

Three prominent multi-scale modelling approaches are: particle-resolved direct numerical simulation (PR-DNS), Euler-Lagrange models (e.g., unresolved CFD-DEM or CFD-DEM), and Euler-Euler models (e.g., TFM) [3]. The PR-DNS method is the most detailed method to model particle-laden flows, since it can resolve all the time and length scales of both phases. At the intermediate level of accuracy of multi-scale modelling approaches, lies the CFD-DEM model. Here, all particles are tracked individually, while a grid size larger than the particle diameter is employed to model the fluid phase using locally averaged Navier-Stokes equations. The least detailed method is the TFM approach, where the fluid phase is modelled in the same manner as CFD-DEM model and the locally averaged Navier-Stokes type equations are applied to resolve the particle phase. In other words, both phases are treated as interpenetrating continua. In both TFM and CFD-DEM approaches, the two-way coupling between the phases is achieved through fluid-particle interphase force closures.

The significantly high computational resources required by PR-DNS, restricts its application to systems with a relatively small number of particles. Thus, the PR-DNS is commonly adopted to study the micro-scale flow features and particularly it has become a tool to derive interphase momentum [4–6] and heat [7,8] exchange closures for less accurate models like CFD-DEM and TFM. The CFD-DEM model is less computationally demanding compared to PR-DNS and particle-particle and particle-wall interactions can be captured precisely using physical models such as soft-sphere [9] or hard-sphere [10] models. Resolving particle-particle and particle-wall contacts increases the computational time of CFD-DEM simulations, which limits their application in simulating systems with more than a few million particles unless huge computational resources are utilized [11]. Despite the enhanced accessibility to supercomputers and their exceptional computational power, the capabilities of CFD-DEM simulations remain inadequate for industrial applications for which the system may contain trillions of particles. Meanwhile, the TFM requires less computational resources, but its accuracy is lower than that of the CFD-DEM model, since it is strongly connected to the particle phase transport coefficients and constitutive relations used in the TFM. The TFM is classified into [12], (1) fine grid TFM approach with high resolution, and (2) coarse grid TFM approaches like filtered-TFM [13] and spatially-averaged TFM [14]. From a performance perspective, the TFM is thus the preferred method to simulate large-scale fluid-particle systems.

There are multiple studies regarding comparing the performance and computational efficiency of the CFD-DEM and the TFM approaches in fluid-particle systems such as fluidized beds [15,16], spouted beds [17,18], and spout fluidized beds [19,20]. All studies have reported that the CFD-DEM exhibits a superior level of accuracy compared to the TFM, while this enhanced accuracy comes at the cost of increased computational demand. Furthermore, the findings indicate that the success of the TFM depends on constitutive closures for kinetic-collisional and frictional solids stresses, as well as particle-wall interactions [19]. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully select the TFM model parameters.

The similarities between PR-DNS and Euler-Lagrange methods in treating the particle phase on the one hand, and Euler-Lagrange and Euler-Euler approaches in treating the fluid phase and the momentum exchange closures on the other hand, has led to the development of hybrid multi-scale models. These models try to simultaneously take advantage of the accuracy of the detailed models and the lower computational demands of the less accurate model. The hybrid multi-scale models are designed in such a way that they concurrently combine a more detailed model with a less accurate one like PR-DNS with CFD-DEM [21] or a continuum approach coupled with a discrete method [22–24].

The development of Coarse-Grain CFD-DEM (CG-CFD-DEM) which

reduces the computational time of CFD-DEM while maintaining high accuracy [25,26], may at first make the development of hybrid multi-scale models appear redundant. However, the geometrical characteristics of the system can impose difficulties in applying large scaling factors for coarse-graining of particles, leading to ineffectiveness or even complete failure of this method in a number of processes. For instance, in fluidized beds with immersed heat exchanger tubes with billions of particles, the geometrical restrictions of the system can impose a great difficulty in using CG-CFD-DEM. This problem can also appear in case of Wurster coaters that are used in pharmaceutical industries. The distance between the bed distributor and the inserted Wurster tube imposes a geometrical restriction on the usage of CG-CFD-DEM and limits the coarse-graining factor to very low numbers [27]. A hybrid model combining continuum approach with a discrete method can be useful in the mentioned cases to provide the information that are only accessible through Lagrangian particles in regions of interested and also improve the accuracy of the continuum approach predictions.

The working principle of these concurrent hybrid multi-scale models available in the literature can be divided into two categories: (1) those that use a “shared domain” approach, where both models are existing in the whole simulation domain, and (2) those that use a “domain decomposition” approach, where the detailed model is only applied in a small sub-domain to improve the predictions of the less detailed model. Here, both models exchange information through a shared reconciliation region and/or a shared boundary.

The hybrid multi-scale models using the “shared domain” approach are common in the literature [28–31]. For instance, Schneiderbauer et al. [32] used a hybrid coarse-grid TFM-DPM model to simulate an industrial-scale cyclone with poly-disperse particles. The coupling between the models was achieved by determining the local Sauter mean diameter from DPM tracers and subsequently applying it to the coarse-grid TFM to evaluate the local drag force (DPM to the coarse-grid TFM step) and using the particle phase stress field from the coarse-grid TFM to obtain the particle-particle contact force in the DPM using a solid-solid drag (coarse-grid TFM to DPM step). Using this hybrid model, they could correctly predict the fractional separation of sub-micrometer particles in the cyclone. A hybrid TFM-DEM model was utilized by Yin et al. [30] to study the particle segregation in a coal beneficiation fluidized bed. The TFM was used to represent the dense solid phase (fine particles) and the DEM was used to model the dilute solid phase (i.e., the beneficiated coal particles (coarse particles)). The particle-particle and particle-wall interactions of the dilute solid phase was handled using a soft-sphere method. The coupling between the two models was realized by incorporating a source term into the momentum equation of the TFM particle phase, which accounted for the influence of discrete particles through solid-solid drag. Similarly, the momentum equation of the discrete particles was also modified by the inclusion of the same force source term. With this hybrid TFM-DEM model they studied the segregation mechanisms and observed that a reduction in the size of discrete particles resulted in a drop in the degree of segregation.

There is a very limited number of studies that have used the “domain decomposition” strategy in the hybrid modelling of fluid-particle flows. Chen et al. [24,33–35] developed a hybrid model to concurrently couple the TFM with the CFD-DEM, where the same fluid phase was used for both models. They applied the CFD-DEM in the vicinity of the channel walls to resolve the particle-wall interactions whereas the TFM was implemented in the central region of the channel. Also, the TFM and the CFD-DEM regions only overlapped in the reconciliation layer where they were exchanging information. They conducted a comparative analysis of the predictions obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, and the hybrid models in terms of time-averaged void fraction profiles, as well as time-averaged solids and fluid velocity profiles. The findings suggest that the hybrid model can improve the accuracy of the TFM predictions, resulting in a closer agreement with the CFD-DEM predictions.

The emergence of a novel hybrid multi-scale modelling methodology within the domain decomposition framework, integrating the TFM and

CFD-DEM methods, gives rise to the following questions: (1) Can a hybrid model be implemented in a specific region of interest in the TFM simulation and resolve the continuum particle phase with discrete particles? (2) Is it feasible to develop a hybrid approach capable of simulating the heterogeneous instabilities observed in particle-laden flows, by using information from the continuum model? (3) Is it possible to develop a hybrid model that can amend the non-physical behavior of the TFM observed in the crossing jet problem?

In this work, we try to answer these questions by introducing a new hybrid multi-scale model based on the domain decomposition framework. This hybrid model applies a CFD-DEM approach within a specific region of interest in a TFM simulation. In the boundaries of the region, the information from the TFM is used to initialize and derive the CFD-DEM simulations while in an inner region away from the boundaries, the CFD-DEM affects the TFM simulation. Furthermore, we will examine the effectiveness of our developed hybrid multi-scale method, in case of particle jets and unbounded fluidization simulations. Also, the results of the CFD-DEM simulations will be adopted as the ground truth to validate the TFM and the new hybrid multi-scale method.

2. Numerical approaches

2.1. TFM

The locally averaged mass and momentum equations for the fluid and the continuum particle phases are written as [36,37],

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_q \rho_q) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_q \rho_q \mathbf{u}_q) = \Omega_{cp} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{u}_f) = -\alpha_f \nabla p_f + \alpha_f \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f - \beta_{TFM}(\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{cp}) + \alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{g} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp}) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp}) = & -\alpha_{cp} \nabla p_f - \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{S}_{cp}^{kc} + \mathbf{S}_{cp}^{fr}) \\ & + \beta_{TFM}(\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{cp}) + \alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{g} + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_{cp} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where in Eq. (1), \mathbf{u}_q , α_q and ρ_q are the velocity, volume fraction and density of the phase q , where q represents either the continuum particle phase or the fluid phase, $q = cp, f$. The variable Ω_{cp} in Eq. (1) represents a semi-implicit source term which will be discussed in section 2.4. The fluid phase pressure is p_f . A Newtonian deviatoric stress is considered for the fluid phase stress-strain tensor, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$ which is,

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_f = 2\mu_f \left(\frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u}_f + \nabla \mathbf{u}_f^T) - \frac{1}{3} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{I} \right) \quad (4)$$

Also, \mathbf{S}_{cp}^{kc} and \mathbf{S}_{cp}^{fr} are the kinetic-collisional and the frictional stress tensors of the continuum particle phase, respectively. The frictional stress tensor is closed using a normal frictional stress and a $\mu(I)$ – rheology models proposed by Chialvo et al. [38]. The frictional stress is considered when $\alpha_{cp} \geq 0.4$. For a comprehensive explanation of the frictional stress model the interested reader is referred to our previous paper [19]. In addition, β_{TFM} denotes the interphase momentum exchange coefficient in the TFM approach. The variable $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{cp}$ in Eq. (3) denotes a semi-implicit source term used in discrete magnification lens and will be described in section 2.4. Table 1 represents the constitutive relations for the TFM approach used in this paper.

2.2. CFD-DEM

Our hybrid multi-scale modelling approach, which will be discussed further below, utilizes the same governing equations for the fluid phase in both the TFM and the CFD-DEM. This allows for the retention of fluid behavior from TFM when switching to CFD-DEM. Only the DEM part is

required for the particles in this case. Therefore, here, we only discuss the momentum balance for the discrete particle phase based on a soft-sphere DEM approach,

$$m_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_{dp,i}}{dt} = \sum_{i \neq j}^n \mathbf{F}_i^{contact} + \mathbf{F}_i^{f-dp} + \mathbf{F}_i^g \quad (18)$$

where m_i and $\mathbf{u}_{dp,i}$ are the particle mass and the particle translational velocity, respectively. In addition, $\mathbf{F}_i^{contact}$ are the particle-particle collisions of surrounding particles j on particle i and particle-wall interactions described by a non-linear Hertzian spring dashpot model [39] with normal and tangential contact forces are presented in Table 2. Furthermore, \mathbf{F}_i^g is the gravitational body force acting on the particle i and particle-fluid interaction forces, \mathbf{F}_i^{f-dp} , considered are,

$$\mathbf{F}_i^{f-dp} = \mathbf{F}_{drag,i} + \mathbf{F}_{\nabla p_f,i} + \mathbf{F}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f,i} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{\nabla p_f,i} = -V_{dp} [\nabla p_f]_{\text{@}i}$ is the pressure gradient force and $\mathbf{F}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f,i} = -V_{dp} [\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f]_{\text{@}i}$ denotes the viscous force originated from the deviatoric fluid phase stress tensor, where V_{dp} is the particle volume, and $\mathbf{F}_{drag,i} = \beta_{DEM} \left([\mathbf{u}_f]_{\text{@}i} - \mathbf{u}_{dp,i} \right)$ is the fluid drag force on particle i , where β_{DEM} is the interphase drag coefficient. Here, $[\]_{\text{@}i}$ means that the fluid phase properties are linearly interpolated to the location of particle i . The Basset force, the virtual mass force, as well as the Saffman and Magnus lift forces are neglected in this paper.

The rotational momentum equation of particle i can be expressed as,

$$I_i \frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{T}_i \quad (20)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$ represents the particle rotational velocity and I_i is the particle moment of inertia, which for spherical particles with radius of R_i is equal to $I_i = \frac{2}{5} m_i R_i^2$. The particle-particle and particle-wall torques, \mathbf{T}_i are calculated as,

$$\mathbf{T}_i = \sum_{i \neq j} R_i \mathbf{n}_{ij} \times \mathbf{F}^f \quad (21)$$

The Lagrangian-Eulerian mapping and subsequent smoothing is important in the CFD-DEM simulations of fluid-particle flows. In this paper, we employ the particle centroid method for Lagrangian-Eulerian mapping, where only the particles whose centres lie inside a cell are considered for calculating the mapped Eulerian fields, e.g., discrete particle volume fraction, discrete particle velocity and interphase momentum exchange coefficient for this cell.

It is found that the smoothing of the mapped Eulerian fields is essential to avoid numerical instabilities, especially in case that particle size is comparable to the computational grid size [41]. Therefore, after obtaining the mapped Eulerian fields, ϕ , a Laplace box filter is employed to smooth these fields,

$$\overline{\phi}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) + \frac{\Delta_{\text{fi}}^2}{24} \nabla^2 \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (34)$$

where \mathbf{e}_i is the unit vector in i -th direction and Δ_{fi} is the filter size which is equal to the computational grid size. In this work, we smooth discrete particle volume fraction, α_{dp} , discrete particle phase velocity field, \mathbf{u}_{dp} , and interphase drag force, $\mathbf{F}_{drag} = \sum_i^n w_{ij} \mathbf{F}_{drag,i} V_{dp,i}$, where $\mathbf{F}_{drag,i}$ is the drag force acting on particle i , n_j , number of particles in the cell j , and w_{ij} is the particle weighting function. The particle weighting function quantifies the influence of particle i on cell j . Note that w_{ij} is computed using the particle centroid method, which is 1 if the center of particle i is within cell j and 0 otherwise. It is noteworthy to mention that for smoothing the \mathbf{u}_{dp} field, the phase-average of $\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}_{dp} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_{dp} \alpha_{dp}}{\alpha_{dp}}$ is used. The reason is to have a weighted contribution of cells. This can be important

Table 1
Constitutive relations of TFM momentum equation [19].

Pseudo-thermal energy equation:

$$\frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \Theta) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp} \Theta) \right) = -\mathbf{S}_{cp}^{kc} : \nabla \mathbf{u}_{cp} - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + \Gamma_{cp} - J_v - \gamma_{\Theta} \quad (5)$$

Kinetic-collisional stress tensor:

$$\mathbf{S}_{cp}^{kc} = \left(P_{cp}^{kc} - \lambda_{cp}^{kc} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D}_{cp}) \right) \mathbf{I} - 2\mu_{cp}^{kc} \text{dev} \mathbf{D}_{cp}, \quad \mathbf{D}_{cp} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\nabla \mathbf{u}_{cp} + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_{cp})^T \right), \quad \text{dev} \mathbf{D}_{cp} = \mathbf{D}_{cp} - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D}_{cp}) \mathbf{I} \quad (6)$$

The continuum particle phase viscosity:

$$\mu_{cp}^{kc} = \left(\frac{2 + \alpha}{3} \right) \left\{ \frac{\mu^*}{g_0 \eta_{cp} (2 - \eta_{cp})} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{l_{cp}}{\mathbb{L}}} + \frac{8}{5} \eta_{cp} \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) \left(1 + \frac{8}{5} \eta_{cp} (3\eta_{cp} - 2) \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) + \frac{3}{5} \eta_{cp} \mu_b \right\} \quad (7)$$

$$\mu^* = \frac{\mu}{1 + \frac{2\beta_{TFM}\mu}{(\alpha_{cp}\rho_{cp})^2 g_0 \Theta}}, \quad \mu = \frac{5\rho_{cp} d_{cp} \sqrt{\pi\Theta}}{96}, \quad \mu_b = \frac{256\mu\alpha_{cp}^2 g_0}{5\pi}, \quad \alpha = \frac{8}{5}, \quad \eta_{cp} = \frac{1}{2} (1 + e_{cp-w}), \quad l_{cp} = \frac{d_{cp}}{6\sqrt{2}g_0\alpha_{cp}} \quad (8)$$

Radial distribution function:

$$g_0 = \frac{1}{1 - \min(\alpha_{cp}, \alpha_{cp}^{min}) / \alpha_{cp}^{max}} \quad (9)$$

Pseudo-thermal energy (PTE) flux vector \mathbf{q} , rate of dissipation of PTE γ_{Θ} , rate of dissipation of PTE by viscous damping J_v and and rate of production of PTE by fluid–particle slip Γ_{cp} :

$$\mathbf{q} = -\frac{\kappa^*}{g_0} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{l_{cp}}{\mathbb{L}}} + \frac{12}{5} \eta_{cp} \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) \left(1 + \frac{12}{5} \eta_{cp}^2 (4\eta_{cp} - 3) \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) + \frac{64}{25\pi} (41 - 33\eta_{cp}) \eta_{cp}^2 \alpha_{cp}^2 g_0^2 \right\} \nabla \Theta, \quad (10)$$

$$\gamma_{\Theta} = \frac{48}{\sqrt{\pi}} \eta_{cp} (1 - \eta_{cp}) \frac{\rho_{cp} \alpha_{cp}^2}{d_{cp}} g_0 \Theta^{3/2}, \quad \kappa^* = \frac{\kappa}{1 + \frac{6\beta_{TFM}\kappa}{5(\alpha_{cp}\rho_{cp})^2 g_0 \Theta}}, \quad \kappa = \frac{75\rho_{cp} d_{cp} \sqrt{\pi\Theta}}{48\eta_{cp} (41 - 33\eta_{cp})}, \quad (11)$$

$$\Gamma_{cp} = \frac{d_{cp} \rho_{cp}^2 \|\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{cp}\|^2}{4\alpha_{cp} g_0 \rho_{cp} \sqrt{\pi\Theta}}, \quad J_v = 3\beta_{TFM}\Theta \quad (12)$$

The continuum particle phase pressure and bulk viscosity:

$$P_{cp}^{kc} = \alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{l_{cp}}{\mathbb{L}}} + 4\eta_{cp} \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) \Theta, \quad \lambda_{cp}^{kc} = \frac{8}{3} \eta_{cp} \alpha_{cp}^2 \rho_{cp} d_{cp} g_0 \sqrt{\frac{\Theta}{\pi}} \quad (13)$$

Boundary conditions for the continuum particle phase:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{kc} = -\eta_w \mu_w \alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} g_0 \Theta \text{erf}(\bar{u}_{cp}) \frac{\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{sl}}{\|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{sl}\|}, \quad \mu_0 = \frac{7}{2} \frac{1 + e_{cp-w}}{1 + \beta_0} \mu_w, \quad \eta_w = \frac{1}{2} (1 + e_{cp-w}), \quad \bar{u}_{cp} = \frac{\|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{sl}\|}{\sqrt{2\Theta\mu_0}}, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{q} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{kc} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{cp}^{sl} - \frac{\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} g_0 \eta_w \sqrt{\Theta}}{\sqrt{2\mu_0^2} \sqrt{\pi}} \exp\left(-\bar{u}_{cp}^2\right) \left\{ \mu_w \left[2\mu_w \|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{sl}\|^2 (2\eta_w - \mu_0) + \Theta (14\mu_w \eta_w - 4\mu_0 (1 + \mu_w) - 6\mu_w \mu_0^2 \eta_w) \right] \right. \\ \left. + \mu_0^2 \sqrt{\Theta} \exp\left(\bar{u}_{cp}^2\right) \left[\sqrt{\Theta} (4(\eta_w - 1) + 6\mu_w^2 \eta_w) - \sqrt{2\pi} \mu_w \|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{sl}\| \text{erf}(\bar{u}_{cp}) \right] \right\} \quad (15)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr} = -\frac{\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{sl}}{\|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{sl}\|} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr,ns} \\ \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr,sl} \end{array} \right. \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr,ns} < \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr,sl} \\ \text{else} \end{array} \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr,ns} = \|\boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr} \cdot \mathbf{n} - (\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr}) \cdot \mathbf{n}\|, \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr,sl} = \mu_w \|\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr} \cdot \mathbf{n}\| \quad (16)$$

The total wall shear stresses:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{fr} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{kc} \quad (17)$$

Table 2
Particle contact forces [40].

Normal contact force exerted on particles:

$$\mathbf{F}^n = -k_n \delta_{n,ij} - \gamma_n \dot{\delta}_{n,ij} \quad (22)$$

Tangential contact force exerted on particles:

$$\mathbf{F}^t = \begin{cases} -k_t \delta_{t,ij} - \gamma_t \dot{\delta}_{t,ij} & |\mathbf{F}^t| < \mu_{dp} |\mathbf{F}^n| \\ -\mathbf{t} \mu_{dp} |\mathbf{F}^n| & |\mathbf{F}^t| \geq \mu_{dp} |\mathbf{F}^n| \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

Particle normal stiffness coefficient:

$$k_n = \frac{4}{3} E^* \sqrt{R^* \delta_{n,ij}} \quad (24)$$

Particle normal damping coefficient:

$$\gamma_n = -\beta \sqrt{5m^* k_n}, \quad \beta = \frac{\ln(e)}{\sqrt{\ln^2(e) + \pi^2}} \quad (25)$$

Particle tangential stiffness coefficient:

$$k_t = 8G^* \sqrt{R^* \delta_{n,ij}} \quad (26)$$

Particle tangential damping coefficient:

$$\gamma_t = -\beta \sqrt{\frac{10}{3} m^* k_t} \quad (27)$$

Normal unit vector along the line of centers of particle i and j :

$$\mathbf{n}_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|} \quad (28)$$

Tangential unit vector along the relative tangential velocity vector of particle i and j :

$$\mathbf{t} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_r}{|\mathbf{u}_r|} \quad (29)$$

Effective Young's modulus (ν is Poisson's ratio):

$$E^* = \left(\frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i} + \frac{1 - \nu_j^2}{E_j} \right)^{-1} \quad (30)$$

Effective shear modulus:

$$G^* = \left(\frac{2 - \nu_i}{G_i} + \frac{2 - \nu_j}{G_j} \right)^{-1} \quad (31)$$

Effective particle radius:

$$R^* = \left(\frac{1}{R_i} + \frac{1}{R_j} \right)^{-1} \quad (32)$$

Effective particle mass:

$$m^* = \left(\frac{1}{m_i} + \frac{1}{m_j} \right)^{-1} \quad (33)$$

for the case of significant gradients of α_{dp} field between the cells.

2.3. Interphase momentum exchange coefficient

In fluid-particle flows where the particle-to-fluid density ratio is significantly greater than one, the drag force becomes the dominant source of the interphase momentum exchange. The drag force is characterized by the particle size, the particle shape, the fluid viscosity and density, and the relative velocity between the fluid and particle. To be consistent with CFD-DEM simulations of Radl and Sundaresan [42] on unbounded fluidization which will be discussed in Section 4.2, the

Beetstra et al. [43] drag model presented in Eq. (35) was chosen. This drag model was obtained from DNS simulations and covers the Reynolds numbers from 20 to 1000 and particle volume fractions up to 0.6. The Reynolds number is $Re = \frac{\alpha_f \beta_f d_s \|\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{cp}\|}{\mu_f}$. Note that in case of the CFD-DEM simulations the Reynolds number is evaluated based on the linearly interpolated fluid phase velocity to the location of the particle, $[\mathbf{u}_f]_{\text{cell}}$, and the smoothed discrete particle velocity, $\overline{\mathbf{u}_{dp,i}}$. In addition, the interphase drag coefficient in the CFD-DEM simulations is $\beta_{DEM} = \beta_{TFM} \pi d_{dp}^3 / 6 [\overline{\alpha_{dp}}]_{\text{cell}}$. To compute the interphase drag coefficient in the CFD-DEM model, the smoothed discrete particle volume fraction, $\overline{\alpha_{dp}}$,

should be evaluated at the location of the particle using the linear interpolation.

$$\beta_{TFM} = 180 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_{cp}^2}{d_{cp}^2 \alpha_f} + 18 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_f^3 \alpha_{cp} (1 + 1.5\sqrt{\alpha_{cp}})}{d_{cp}^2} + 0.31 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_{cp} Re [\alpha_f^{-1} + 3\alpha_f \alpha_{cp} + 8.4 Re^{-0.343}]}{d_{cp}^2 \alpha_f [1 + 10^{3\alpha_{cp}} Re^{-0.5 - 2\alpha_{cp}}]} \quad (35)$$

2.4. Hybrid multi-scale modelling approach

Concurrently coupling the TFM with the CFD-DEM allows to leverage the benefits of both approaches and achieve an optimal balance between speed-up and accuracy. Therefore, for the first time, we introduce a hybrid model based on the domain decomposition framework, wherein, the TFM simulation governs the embedded CFD-DEM simulation since it covers the whole computational domain. Unlike the other hybrid models based on the domain decomposition framework available in the literature [24,33–35], in our hybrid model, the CFD-DEM is nested into a TFM simulation. In other words, the CFD-DEM acts like a magnification lens and magnifies the continuum particle phase by using the discrete particles in a specific region of interest. We will refer to this sub-domain as the discrete magnification lens region throughout this study. The fluid phase is shared between the models in such a way that the fluid phase is solved in the TFM side but takes into account the presence of the discrete particles in the CFD-DEM domain. This will be discussed further below in detail. We refer this hybrid model as the “discrete magnification lens”, but for brevity throughout this paper, we will use the abbreviation “DML”. In this study, DML is applied in case of mono-disperse, isothermal and non-reacting flows.

The schematic of the DML region is illustrated in Fig. 1. The region indicated with the cyan color represents a TFM simulation and the region wrapped inside the overlapping boundary marked by the green color is the CFD-DEM domain. It should be noted that although Fig. 1 represents the schematic of the DML region in two dimensions, the TFM and the CFD-DEM domains are indeed three-dimensional regions. It is obvious that in order to drive a CFD-DEM simulation nested into a TFM analysis, certain information from TFM should be transferred to CFD-DEM. Note that at the DML region, TFM and CFD-DEM simulations use the same computational grid. The size of the DML region is determined by the flow characteristics of the system, such as the length scale of the heterogeneous instabilities (will be discussed in section 4.2) and the geometrical features of the region where the DML approach is used. The roles of different sections of the schematic illustrated in Fig. 1 are explained in the following.

Fig. 1. The schematic of the DML region. The cyan is the TFM simulation domain. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

The overlapping boundary depicted with the green color is the shared border between the TFM and the CFD-DEM domains. It consists of the outer surface of the initial layer of the computational grid cells in the CFD-DEM domain. This boundary is used to measure the entering mass flux of the continuum particle phase to the CFD-DEM on each cell face. Using the measured mass flux of the continuum particle phase at the cell faces, the number of discrete particles to be inserted into the CFD-DEM domain can be calculated by,

$$n_{dp,f} = \left(\mathbf{S}_f \cdot (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp})_f \right) \Delta t_{coupling} / m_i \quad (36)$$

where, $n_{dp,f}$ is the number of discrete particles to be inserted from the cell face f , $\mathbf{S}_f \cdot (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp})_f$ is the continuum particle phase mass flux on the cell face f , which is calculated based on the discretization of the advection term in Eq. (3) using the finite volume method, \mathbf{S}_f is the cell face normal vector, and m_i represents the mass of discrete particle i . The coupling time step between the TFM and the CFD-DEM simulations in the DML is $\Delta t_{coupling}$, which is equal to the TFM time step and the CFD time step of the CFD-DEM model. Note that $n_{dp,f}$ is always rounded towards the least integer number, since it is not feasible to insert fractions of a particle. In each coupling time step, the residues remaining from the rounding operator for each cell face f are stored and added to the corresponding face mass flux in the subsequent coupling time step.

The insertion region indicated by the blue color, represents the region where the discrete particles are inserted. As illustrated, this region is made up of the first layer of cells near to the overlapping boundary, with each cell belonging to a different boundary face. Consequently, the particles to be inserted based on Eq. (36) from each cell face f are inserted into their respective cells using the algorithm explained by Queteschiner et al. [40,44]. Upon insertion of new discrete particles, it is necessary to assign an initial velocity vector. This initial velocity vector can be obtained by randomly sampling from the Maxwellian velocity distribution. This is because in the derivation of Eq. (5) based on the kinetic theory of granular flows, the Chapman-Enskog equations are solved under the assumption of the Maxwellian particle velocity distribution. Hence, the initial values of discrete particle velocity vector can be obtained from,

$$f(\mathbf{u}_{dp,i} - \mathbf{u}_{cp}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\Theta)^{3/2}} e^{-\left[\frac{(\mathbf{u}_{dp,i} - \mathbf{u}_{cp})^2}{2\Theta} \right]} \quad (37)$$

where Θ and \mathbf{u}_{cp} are the granular temperature calculated from Eq. (5) and the continuum particle phase velocity obtained from solving Eq. (3) in the underlying TFM simulation, respectively. These variables are unique to the cell into which the particle will be inserted. Finally, $\mathbf{u}_{dp,i}$ is the randomly sampled velocity vector from the Maxwellian distribution (Eq. (37)) and is assigned as the initial velocity of discrete particle i . Note that since the particle rotational velocity is not available from the TFM, zero initial value is considered for the inserted discrete particles.

The particle velocity controller region is represented by the red color. In this region, the velocity of discrete particles is adjusted to minimize deviation from the continuum particle phase velocity in the cell corresponding to the particle's position. The continuum particle phase velocity is obtained from the underlying TFM simulations by solving Eq. (3). It should be noted that the particle velocity controller region should include the insertion region, and can span up to multiple layers. Because newly inserted particles may be inserted too close to already existing particles in the cell, jittering of the particles may occur; thus, the insertion and particle velocity controller regions are considered overlapping. The velocity of discrete particles is controlled by applying a force on each particle which is defined as,

$$F_{controller,i} = \rho_{dp} V_{dp} \left([\mathbf{u}_{cp}]_{\text{cell } i} - [\overline{\mathbf{u}_{dp}}]_{\text{cell } i} \right) / \Delta t_{coupling} \quad (38)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}$ is the mapped and smoothed discrete particle velocity. By controlling the discrete particle velocity in this way, we actually sustain the particle velocity fluctuations and only modify the mean velocity value. It is clear that this force is proportional to the relative velocity between the discrete and the continuum particle phase velocities. It should be noted that the continuum particle phase velocity is interpolated to the position of the discrete particle. This controlling force is also applied to every particle whose center is within the particle velocity controller region.

The *relaxation region* is marked purple. To alleviate the possible disturbances on the discrete particles caused by the imposed forces on the particles, such as fluid-particle interaction forces and controller forces. In this region, the discrete particles are only subjected to the fluid-particle interaction and particle-particle and particle-wall contact forces as outlined in Eq. (18), with no additional forces acting upon them.

The *two-way coupling region* presented with the orange color. Up to this point, the information provided from the underlying TFM simulation has driven the CFD-DEM simulation in a one-way coupled manner; in the two-way coupling region, the discrete particles' information is used to influence the underlying TFM simulation, resulting in a two-way coupling between the TFM and the CFD-DEM models. In one-way coupling, the TFM's information, including the mass flux of the continuum particle phase, continuum particle phase velocity, granular temperature, and fluid phase velocity, is transferred to the CFD-DEM side (TFM to CFD-DEM) to conduct the CFD-DEM simulation. Two-way coupling refers to the additional process of transferring information from the CFD-DEM to the TFM using semi-implicit source terms defined in Eq. (1) and (3), as well as the interphase momentum exchange term in Eq. (2)–(3). Note that this coupling concept is different from the fluid-particle coupling concepts in which the interactions between the particle and the fluid phases determines the type of the coupling (e.g., four-way coupling). To accomplish the two-way coupling via the DML, we introduce two possible methodologies taking into account different application scenarios:

1. Mass and momentum coupling can be used in the case that the TFM approach is unable to capture the physical behavior of the system. We will refer to this methodology as “DML (mmc)” throughout this paper.
2. Momentum coupling is used in cases where the TFM still reveals appropriate behavior but there is room for improvement of the predictions. This method will be referred to “DML (mc)” in this paper.

In the DML (mmc) model, the information from the CFD-DEM model affects the continuum particle phase mass equation (Eq. (1)), the continuum particle phase velocity (Eq. (3)) and the interphase momentum exchange term in the continuum particle phase and fluid momentum equations (Eq. (2)–(3)). This methodology can be considered as a highly intrusive approach due to enforcing a semi-implicit source term, Ω_{cp} , to the continuum particle phase mass equation (Eq. (1)). This source term steers the continuum particle volume fraction field of the underlying TFM towards the discrete particle volume fraction field calculated from the discrete particles like the direct forcing concept in immersed boundary method [45]. The term Ω_{cp} can be described as,

$$\Omega_{cp} = \rho_{cp} \left(\overline{\alpha}_{dp}^n - \alpha_{cp}^{n+1} \right) / \Delta t_{coupling} \quad (39)$$

where $\overline{\alpha}_{dp}^n$ is the explicit mapped and smoothed discrete particle volume fraction and α_{cp}^{n+1} is the implicit continuum particle volume fraction of the TFM. To take into account the presence of the discrete particles in the continuum particle phase momentum equation (Eq. (3)), a semi-implicit source term, Ψ_{cp} , is added to the RHS of Eq. (3). This source term drives the continuum particle phase velocity of the underlying TFM

towards the discrete particle velocity field. The term Ψ_{cp} is defined as,

$$\Psi_{cp} = \alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \left(\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{n+1} - \overline{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}^n \right) / \Delta t_{coupling} \quad (40)$$

where \mathbf{u}_{cp}^{n+1} is the implicit continuum particle phase velocity of the TFM model that Eq. (3) is solved for. Also, $\overline{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}^n$ is the explicit discrete particle velocity obtained from the CFD-DEM model in the previous time step, n . In addition, in the two-way coupling region, the interphase momentum exchange coefficient of the continuum particle phase and fluid phases, β_{TFM} , as depicted in Eq. (2)–(3), is replaced by the interphase momentum exchange coefficient obtained from the CFD-DEM simulations, K^{f-dp} . The interphase momentum exchange coefficient in the CFD-DEM model is computed based on the interphase drag forces of the particles, $\mathbf{F}_{drag,i}$, which are mapped to the computational grid with respect to the particle weighting function, w_{ij} , and subsequently smoothed. The term K^{f-dp} can be expressed as [46],

$$K^{f-dp} = \frac{1}{V_j} \frac{\| \overline{\mathbf{F}}_{drag} \|}{\| \mathbf{u}_f - \overline{\mathbf{u}}_{dp} \|} \quad (41)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{F}}_{drag}$ is the interphase drag force field, and V_j is the volume of cell j .

In the DML (mc), we eliminate the semi-implicit source term, Ω_{cp} , from the RHS of Eq. (1) and we only consider the effect of the discrete particles on the continuum particle phase momentum equation (Eq. (3)) using the same procedure as in the DML (mmc) model.

3. Numerical implementation

3.1. Solution procedure

The TFM simulations are performed in OpenFOAM using a modified version of the *twoPhaseEulerFoam* solver named *twoPhaseEulerTurbFoam* [19]. We employ a four-way coupling CFD-DEM framework in which fluid-particle, particle-fluid interaction, particle-particle, and particle-wall interactions are considered. In the CFD-DEM simulations, OpenFOAM solves the fluid phase equations on an Eulerian grid while the particles are tracked individually using LIGGGHTS in a Lagrangian framework. The coupling between the discrete particle and fluid phases is achieved through CFDEMcoupling [47]. In OpenFOAM, the finite volume method is used for spatial discretization, where a collocated grid is applied, meaning that all variables are calculated and stored at the center of the grid cells. The use of a collocated grid causes the pressure-velocity decoupling problem, which is handled in OpenFOAM using the Rhie-Chow correction [48]. The PIMPLE algorithm which is the combination of Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equations (SIMPLE) method and Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operators (PISO) method was utilized for the pressure-velocity coupling of the Navier–Stokes equations. In this work, the numerical methods have been implemented in parallel using message passing interface (MPI).

Fig. 2. The schematic of the discrete magnification lens model implementation for a single time step.

3.2. Implementation of the discrete magnification lens model

This section summarizes the solution procedure used in our DML code. Fig. 2 illustrates the schematic of the DML model in one time step. It can be deduced that the time step of TFM, Δt_{TFM} , is equal to the CFD time step of CFD-DEM, Δt_{CFD} , which is the coupling time step between TFM and CFD-DEM, $\Delta t_{coupling}$. As illustrated, the DML model consists of four consecutive parts: (1) the TFM simulation, (2) the transfer of information from the TFM to the CFD-DEM, (3) the CFD-DEM simulation, and (4) transfer of information from the CFD-DEM to the TFM. Consequently, the solution procedure is divided into four sections with substeps as presented below:

1. The TFM simulation
 - (a) Specify the initial and boundary conditions
 - (b) Solve the continuum particle phase mass equation with semi-implicit source term, Ω_{cp} , (Eq. (39)) in case of DML (mmc) model, or without Ω_{cp} in case of DML (mc) model using the Multidimensional Universal Limiter with Explicit Solution (MULES [49]) method to obtain α_{cp} (Eq. (1))
 - (c) Compute $\alpha_f = 1.0 - \alpha_{cp}$
 - (d) Discretize and linearize the momentum equations (Eq. (2)–(3))
 - (e) Solve the pressure equation using the PIMPLE [50] algorithm
 - (f) Obtain \mathbf{u}_f , \mathbf{u}_{cp} , and p_f fields
2. The information transfer from the TFM to the CFD-DEM simulation
 - (a) Specify the CFD-DEM region boundaries
 - (b) Measure the entering mass flux of the continuum particle phase through faces of the CFD-DEM region boundaries
 - (c) Select the values of Θ and \mathbf{u}_{cp} in the adjacent cells to the CFD-DEM region boundaries
 - (d) Transfer $\mathbf{S}_f \cdot (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp})_f$ to LIGGGHTS through CFDEMcoupling framework
3. The CFD-DEM simulation
 - (a) Insert the discrete particles based on Eq. (36) and assign the initial velocity value using a random value from the Maxwellian distribution (Eq. (37))
 - (b) Compute forces acting on a particle (Eq. (18)) and if the particle center is in the particle velocity controller region apply an additional controller force to it (Eq. (38))
 - (c) Update position, velocity, and angular velocity of the particles with the time integration of Eq. (18) and (20) using the velocity Verlet scheme in the DEM time steps
 - (d) Localize particles on the Eulerian grid
 - (e) Compute the mapped discrete particle phase volume fraction (α_{dp}) from particles with the particle centroid method
 - (f) Calculate the mapped discrete particle phase velocity (\mathbf{u}_{dp}) based on the particle weighting function determined by the particle mapping method
 - (g) Smoothen α_{dp} and \mathbf{u}_{dp} fields (Eq. (34))
 - (h) Compute the fluid-particle forces (Eq. (19)) to be used in the next DEM time steps using the fluid phase fields obtained from the TFM (e.g., \mathbf{u}_f and p_f)
 - (i) Map the computed interphase drag forces of the particles to the Eulerian grid and smooth it to obtain, $\overline{\mathbf{F}}_{drag}$ field
 - (j) Calculate the mapped interphase momentum exchange coefficient, K^{f-dp} (Eq. (41)) and smoothen it (Eq. (34))
4. The information transfer from the CFD-DEM to the TFM simulation
 - (a) Specify the two-way coupling region
 - (b) Transfer the mapped and subsequently smoothed particle phase velocity field, $\overline{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}$, and the mapped interphase momentum exchange coefficient field, K^{f-dp} to the TFM
 - (c) Use $\overline{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}$ field in the semi-implicit source term, Ψ_{cp} (Eq. (40))
 - (d) Replace the interphase momentum exchange coefficient in the momentum equations of the TFM, β_{TFM} , with K^{f-dp} field in the two-way coupling region

4. Results

4.1. Particle jets

A highly effective test case for examining the constraints of the TFM models derived with Chapman-Enskog expansion is the particle-trajectory test [51–53], in which two streams of particles are introduced into a channel and their interaction is determined by their respective particle volume fractions. In particular, dilute particle jets with particle volume fraction below around 0.05, should cross with only minor interaction, since particle collisions are not dominant. The moderately dense and dense particle jets with particle volume fraction above 0.05 show higher interactions between the jets due to increased particle collisions. These behaviors can be easily captured using Euler-Lagrange models, since the momentum of each particle is altered only if a particle-particle collision occurs. However, in TFM, opposite momentum fluxes entering the impingement point are averaged into a single local particle momentum value, resulting in an unrealistic merging of the particle jets independent of the particle volume fractions of the jets.

Thus, we investigate the performance of the CFD-DEM, the TFM, and the DML in case of dilute, moderately dense and dense particle jets. It has to be mentioned that the predictions of the CFD-DEM simulations are used as reference for numerical verification of the TFM and the DML. The schematic of the geometry of the channel is presented in Fig. 3. In the simulations, two diagonal jets with 45-degree angle and velocity of 14 m s^{-1} were injected from the opposite sides of a channel. The fluid flow entered with a velocity of 25 m s^{-1} and left through the top outlet. In all simulations, uniform fluid velocity was specified at the inlet of the channel, and atmospheric pressure was used as boundary condition at the top outlet. Moreover, a no-slip boundary condition was applied to the fluid phase velocity at the walls. To eliminate any effect of particles falling down towards the bottom of the box we ignored the influence of gravity in our simulations. This helps to isolate the core phenomenon of crossing particle jets problem. The drag model of Beetstra et al. [43] was applied. The domain was discretized by $30 \times 1 \times 60$ ($n_x \times n_y \times n_z$) hexahedral cells with a size of $1.5d_p$. The simulation parameters and material properties are listed in Table 3. The Δt_{TFM} and Δt_{CFD} were chosen in a way to keep the maximum Courant number well below 1.0. Also, Δt_{DEM} was small enough to prevent large and unphysical overlaps between contacting particles. All simulations presented in this section were performed using second order spatial accuracy for both diffusion (Gauss linear [50]) and advection (SuperBee [50]) terms in the Navier-Stokes equations. Time advancement is accomplished

Fig. 3. The schematic of the particle jets channel.

Table 3
Material properties and simulation parameters for particle jets simulations.

Property	value	Unit
d_p	2	mm
μ_f	1.8×10^{-5}	$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
ρ_f	1.3	kg m^{-3}
ρ_s	1000	kg m^{-3}
e_{p-p}	0.8	–
e_{p-w}	0.95	–
μ_{p-p}	0.05	–
μ_{p-w}	0.05	–
ν (CFD-DEM)	0.3	–
E (CFD-DEM)	5.0×10^7	$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-2}$
Δt_{TFM}	5.0×10^{-6}	s
Δt_{CFD}	5.0×10^{-6}	s
Δt_{DEM}	1.0×10^{-7}	s
$\Delta t_{coupling}$	5.0×10^{-6}	s
Simulation time	2	s
Time-averaging window	1.5	s

using the second order accurate backward scheme [50]. It needs to be mentioned that in the DML simulations, the two-way coupling between the TFM and the CFD-DEM was activated at the initial time of the simulation.

4.1.1. Dilute particle jets

The time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles of the jets with volume fraction of 0.02 are presented in Fig. 4. It is evident that in CFD-DEM, particle jets are crossing showing only minor interaction, whereas this is not observed in the TFM. This defect can be attributed to the formulation of the TFM approach lacking a bi-modal velocity distribution required for the representation of the crossing jet. The particle volume fraction profiles of the DML illustrate that nesting CFD-DEM in the region of the jet crossing can correct the behavior of the TFM simulation. It is obvious that in the DML simulations similar to the CFD-DEM, the jets cross each other without merging into a single dense jet.

The two-way coupling region of the DML is represented by red solid lines in Fig. 4. Since we are interested in studying the jet crossing region, the DML region was selected in a way to solely cover the area where the jets interact. Therefore, similar to the TFM, the DML simulations are showing a wrong behavior in the vicinity of the walls above the magnified region. The location of the overlapping boundary, insertion, particle velocity controller, relaxation and two-way coupling regions are illustrated in more detail in Fig. 5a. The overlapping boundary is located at $z = 0.024$ m and one cell layer on top of it is used as insertion region ($z = 0.024 - 0.027$ m). The particle velocity controller region including three cell layers, spans from $z = 0.024$ m to $z = 0.033$ m and the two cell layers of the relaxation region cover the range between $z = 0.033$ m and $z = 0.039$ m. The two-way coupling region comprises thirteen cell layers, starting from $z = 0.039$ m to $z = 0.078$ m. For the particle jets simulations, this combination of the particle velocity controller,

relaxation and two-way coupling regions appeared to be sufficient. An instantaneous snapshot of the DML simulation can be seen in Fig. 5b, where the discrete particles can be detected on top of the particle volume fraction field of the TFM.

In order to investigate the results in a quantitative manner, the time-averaged particle volume fraction obtained from the simulations represented in Fig. 6. Fig. 6a includes the time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles at the location of overlapping boundary ($z = 0.024$ m). Two distinct particle jets are visible in the plots, and the results of the TFM and the DML simulations are coinciding, due to adopting the same TFM simulation set-up in these models. Moreover, the profiles of the TFM and the DML simulations indicate a more diffusive particle volume fraction field compared to CFD-DEM. This is attributed to the higher physical (since $\mu_{cp} \neq 0$) and numerical diffusion of TFM simulations [52]. Measuring particle volume fraction at $z = 0.09$ m (outside the magnification region), indicates that the TFM simulation is behaving completely wrong, while the CFD-DEM and the DML simulations predict particle jet crossing correctly. To further assess the results, we may calculate the relative root mean square error using,

$$\%e_r = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\alpha_{cp,i} - \bar{\alpha}_{dp,i})^2}{N}}}{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_{dp,i}}{N}} \times 100 \quad (42)$$

where N is the number of data points, $\alpha_{cp,i}$ is the continuum particle volume fraction from the TFM and the DML simulations, and $\bar{\alpha}_{dp,i}$ is the smoothed discrete particle volume fraction from the CFD-DEM simulations.

Evaluating the e_r values of the TFM and the DML simulations against the CFD-DEM data (Table 4) reveals that overall the DML methods significantly reduce the large relative error of the TFM (178.82%) to below 22.0% at $z = 0.09$ m. The particle volume fraction profiles along the channel height at $x = 0.045$ m are depicted in Fig. 6c. Although the DML and the CFD-DEM simulations are predicting a similar trend, the TFM exhibits totally different trend with the highest discrepancy compared to the CFD-DEM results (cf. Table 4). Both DML simulations are in good agreement with the CFD-DEM predictions and have decreased the relative TFM error from 284.53% to below 33% as listed in Table 4.

In the intersection region of the jets, the particle volume fraction of discrete particles in the DML (mmc) simulation matches well with the one from the underlying TFM simulation. However, the particle volume fraction of discrete particles in the DML (mc) simulation, does not fit with underlying TFM. This is due to neglecting the semi-implicit mass source term as given in Eq. (1) in the DML (mc) simulation.

At the end of the channel an increase in the particle volume fraction can be noticed in the CFD-DEM simulation. This is due to the reflection of the jets from the channel walls which does not occur in the TFM and DML simulations. Hence, part of the relative error of the DML simulations is related to this uncaptured effect. While this leads to an increase

Fig. 4. Time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles in dilute particle jets obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, the DML (mc), and the DML (mmc).

Fig. 5. (a) Schematic of the DML region, (b) Instantaneous snapshot of the DML (mmc) simulation with discrete particles.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the time-averaged particle volume fraction obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, DML (mc) methodology, and DML (mmc) methodology in dilute particle jets. The horizontal profiles: (a) $z = 0.024$ m, (b) $z = 0.09$ m, and the vertical profile: (c) $x = 0.045$ m. Note that in (c), the dotted lines are representing the discrete particle volume fraction from CFD-DEM part of the DML simulations.

Table 4

The e_r values of the TFM and the DML against CFD-DEM for a selection of particle volume fractions.

Particle volume fraction	$z = 0.09$ m			$x = 0.045$ m		
	TFM	DML (mc)	DML (mmc)	TFM	DML (mc)	DML (mmc)
0.02	178.82%	18.11%	21.13%	284.53%	32.77%	30.78%
0.05	59.53%	31.91%	23.48%	83.80%	27.51%	19.25%
0.15	12.41%	-	-	10.29%	-	-

of the particle volume fraction in the downstream of the impingement point in the CFD-DEM, this does not happen in the DML simulations, because we have deliberately chosen the DML region to only correct the crossing jets and accept further error outside this region.

4.1.2. Moderately dense particle jets

As we keep the fluid and particle jet velocities constant and increase the particle volume fraction to 0.05, the particle flow pattern changes as illustrated in Fig. 7. This results in more particle collisions at the jets impingement point, leading to scattering of the particles in the rest of the domain. This behavior is visible in all simulations, however in the TFM simulation, a high concentration of particles can be seen in the impingement region. This is due to the lack of bi-modal velocity

distribution in the TFM which leads to merging of the jets to some degree. However, this problem does not exist in the profiles of DML simulations, implying that this model is capable of correcting the unphysical behavior of TFM.

To justify our argument about effectiveness of the DML simulations, we further study the particle volume fraction profiles at different heights as displayed in Fig. 8. Diffusive particle volume fraction in the jets can be observed from the TFM and the DML simulations at $z = 0.024$ m (Fig. 8a) similar to the dilute particle jets. Although some degree of merging of the jets occurs in the TFM, as demonstrated in Fig. 8b, the DML results are in better agreement with the CFD-DEM simulations.

A comparison between the e_r values of the DML and the CFD-DEM at $z = 0.09$ m reveals that the DML (mmc) is showing superior accuracy to the DML (mc) (refer to Table 4). The DML (mmc) and the DML (mc) decrease the relative error of the TFM from 59.54% to 23.48% and 31.91%, respectively. The variation of the particle volume fraction profiles along the channel height (Fig. 8c) is similar between the simulations. However, the particle volume fraction in the impingement region is significantly larger in the TFM simulations. The distribution of particle volume fraction in the CFD-DEM is narrower than in the DML. Still, the DML (mmc) and the DML (mc) simulations reduce the relative error of the TFM (83.80%) to 19.25% and 27.51%, respectively. Also, the particle volume fraction of discrete particles is completely in line with the values from the underlying TFM in case of using the DML

Fig. 7. Time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles in moderately dense particle jets calculated from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, the DML (mc) methodology, and DML (mmc) methodology.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the time-averaged particle volume fraction obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, DML (mc) methodology, and DML (mmc) methodology in moderately dense particle jets. The horizontal profiles: (a) $z = 0.024$ m, (b) $z = 0.09$ m, and the vertical profile: (c) $x = 0.045$ m. It needs to be mentioned in (c), the dotted lines are representing the discrete particle volume fraction from the CFD-DEM part of the DML simulations.

(mmc) method. This is not the case for the DML (mc) method.

4.1.3. Dense particle jets

By increasing the particle volume fraction of particle jets to 0.15, one should expect more particle collisions increasing the loss of particles' energy, which leads to a merging of the jets into a dense stream as demonstrated in Fig. 9. However, downstream of the impingement

Fig. 9. Time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles in dense particle jets obtained from the CFD-DEM and the TFM.

point, particle collisions cause a scattering particles away from the center of the channel. It is clear that in dense particle flows, TFM behaves similar to the CFD-DEM, implying the applicability of the TFM in dense particle-laden flows. Since the results of the TFM are in a good agreement with the CFD-DEM, then there is no need to apply DML here. This can also be deduced from Fig. 10, where the particle volume fraction profiles of the TFM correspond well to the ones of the CFD-DEM at $z = 0.024$ m, $z = 0.09$ m, and $x = 0.045$ m. Also, the e_r values in Table 4 for dense particle jets, confirm the good agreement of the TFM results to the CFD-DEM ones.

4.1.4. Numerical costs

The numerical costs related to the CFD-DEM, the TFM, the DML (mc), and the DML (mmc) approaches for 1 s of calculations on 4-core CPU with 3.1 GHz frequency are provided in Table 5. As expected, CFD-DEM entails higher numerical cost compared to TFM and it increases with higher particle volume fraction. In comparison to the CFD-DEM simulations the DML approaches show some degree of speed up. In case of dilute particle jets, about 6.9% speed up is achieved with DML approaches compared to the CFD-DEM, where it was about 3.76% for the moderately dense particle jets simulations. Compared to the corresponding CFD-DEM simulation, there is no significant speed up achieved by the DML approach. However, this case demonstrates the benefit of adopting the DML approaches in a case that the TFM has a completely non-physical behavior. The difference between the computational costs of the TFM and the DML approaches is related to methodological

Fig. 10. Comparison of the time-averaged particle volume fraction obtained from the CFD-DEM and the TFM in dense particle jets. The horizontal profiles: (a) $z = 0.024$ m, (b) $z = 0.09$ m, and the vertical profile: (c) $x = 0.045$ m.

Table 5

CPU time of the CFD-DEM, the TFM, the DML (mc) and the DML (mmc) approaches for particle jet simulations with various particle volume fractions.

Dilute				moderately dense				Dense	
DEM	TFM	DML (mc)	DML (mmc)	DEM	TFM	DML (mc)	DML(mmc)	DEM	TFM
7.68 h	6.51 h	7.15 h	7.17 h	8.23 h	6.51 h	7.92 h	7.95 h	11.78 h	6.51 h

overhead. This includes the communication of data from the TFM to the CFD-DEM and vice versa, the discrete particle insertion algorithm, the calculations of the various forces on discrete particles, contact detection, and integration of the discrete particles' equations of motion.

4.2. Unbounded fluidization

Unbounded fluidization (also known as sedimentation) is adopted to replicate clusters of particles in fluid-particle systems and is characterized by a relative velocity between the particle and the fluid phases. The clusters are defined as persistent, transient and heterogeneous structures of particles and considerably impact mass, momentum and energy transport in the system [54]. These clusters and streamers of particles form because of (i) inertia between the particle phase, gravity and particle-fluid drag, and (ii) dissipation of fluctuating energy of particles due to inelastic collisions and viscous damping [55]. Usually, in unbounded fluidization simulations, no forces act in the transverse directions, whereas a constant body force, i.e. gravity, acts in negative z-direction. The fluid pressure is divided into a fluctuating (local) component superimposed by a linear gradient, where the latter opposes gravity and supports the weight of the suspension, i.e. [42],

$$\nabla p_f = \left(\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d \rho_p + \left(1 - \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d \right) \rho_f \right) \mathbf{g} \quad (43)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle_d$ denotes the domain average operator. This force is added as an additional body force to the particles and the fluid, so that no net acceleration occurs and the system stays statistically steady.

A significant challenge in accurately modelling fluid-particle systems is clustering. It has been shown in the literature that the CFD-DEM and the TFM simulations are capable of capturing the dynamic behavior of the clusters [42,54,56]. However, according to findings of Fullmer and Hrenya [54], the domain-averaged slip velocity values of the TFM show relative errors of less than 20% compared to the CFD-DEM results over a range of particle volume fractions. In this section, our aim is to assess the ability of the DML model in reproducing the particle clusters and improving the TFM predictions. Unlike the previous studies [54,56] in addition to comparing the domain-averaged slip velocity in the vertical

direction, $\langle \mathbf{u}_{slip} \rangle_d$, with the CFD-DEM data, we extend the comparison to the domain-averaged variance of particle volume fraction, $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d = \langle \alpha_p \alpha_p \rangle_d - \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$, and turbulent kinetic energy of the particle phase, $\langle \mathbf{k}_p \rangle_d = 1/2 \left(\langle \mathbf{u}_p \mathbf{u}_p \rangle_{p,d} - \langle \mathbf{u}_p \rangle_{p,d} \langle \mathbf{u}_p \rangle_{p,d} \right)$ where $\langle \mathbf{u}_p \rangle_{p,d} = \langle \alpha_p \mathbf{u}_p \rangle_d / \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$. In contrast to the previous studies [54,56] that have adopted the CFD-DEM results of Radl and Sundaresan [42], in the present work the CFD-DEM simulations were performed using our in-house developed CFD-DEM code.

4.2.1. Numerical validation

We validate our CFD-DEM predictions of the unbounded fluidization of Geldart A particle with the ones from Radl and Sundaresan work [42] in a 3D periodic domain with the size of $0.008 \text{ m} \times 0.008 \text{ m} \times 0.032 \text{ m}$. Periodic boundary conditions are applied on box faces along x-, y- and z-directions. The TFM results are validated against our CFD-DEM simulations. Results of the CFD-DEM simulations are the ideal type of data for numerical validation of the TFM, since like TFM, in CFD-DEM, the flow around the particle phase is not resolved and this allows to apply the same drag force closure in both approaches. This method of numerical validation of the TFM isolates the validation of the continuum closures (kinetic-collisional solids stress, the frictional solids stress, and so forth).

In the TFM simulations of unbounded fluidization, the solids conductivity closure was based on the work of Hrenya and Sinclair [57] and the solids pressure closure of Lun et al. [58] was used. Other closures were adopted according to Table 1.

The material properties and model parameters used in the simulation are listed in Table 6. Different domain-averaged particle volume fractions of 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, and 0.20 were simulated using the CFD-DEM and the TFM approaches. The corresponding number of discrete particles related to domain-averaged particle volume fractions of 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, and 0.2 is 463,572, 927,145, 1,390,717, and 1,854,289, respectively. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in all three directions. The grid discretization size was chosen based on the Radl and Sundaresan work [42], and was $32 \times 32 \times 128$ ($n_x \times n_y \times n_z$) in all simulations which is equal to $3.33d_p$.

Table 6

Material properties and simulation parameters for the unbounded fluidization simulations.

Property	value	Unit
d_p	75	μm
μ_f	1.8×10^{-5}	$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
ρ_f	1.3	kg m^{-3}
ρ_p	1500	kg m^{-3}
e_{p-p}	0.9	–
μ_{p-p}	0.1	–
ν (CFD-DEM)	0.42	–
E (CFD-DEM)	1.0×10^6	$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-2}$
Δt_{TFM}	5.0×10^{-5}	s
Δt_{CFD}	5.0×10^{-5}	s
Δt_{DEM}	1.0×10^{-6}	s
$\Delta t_{coupling}$	5.0×10^{-5}	s

All simulations of this section were conducted using second order spatial accuracy for both diffusion (Gauss linear [50]) and advection (SuperBee [50]) terms in the Navier–Stokes equations. Time advancement is accomplished using the second order accurate backward scheme [50]. The relaxation factors in the PIMPLE loop for fluid phase velocity and pressure were 0.6 and 0.3, respectively. Initially, the particle phase is distributed randomly in the system to reduce the required simulation time to reach to the statistical steady state. Selecting the proper time step for the CFD-DEM and the TFM simulations of unbounded fluidization of Geldart A particles is of utmost importance for the convergence of the solution.

Typically, in CFD-DEM simulations time integration of the particle-particle contact equations limits the choice of the time step. The Rayleigh criterion is based on the principle that contact energy cannot propagate beyond the in-contact neighbouring particles in a single time step and reads as [59],

$$t_R = \frac{\pi R \sqrt{\rho_p / G}}{0.1631\nu + 0.8766} \quad (44)$$

where t_R is Rayleigh time, and shear modulus, G , is $G = E/2(1 + \nu)$. Typically in DEM simulations, 10 to 20% of Rayleigh time is used as the DEM time step [60]. In our simulations, $t_R = 8.14 \times 10^{-6}$ s, thus the Δt_{DEM} is about 12% of t_R . In the CFD-DEM simulations, in addition to Rayleigh time criterion, particle relaxation time, τ_p , also needs to be checked. Particle relaxation time, τ_p , or particle response time with assuming Stokes drag law can enforce the upper bound of Δt_{DEM} [46] and is defined as,

$$\tau_p = \frac{d_p^2 \rho_p}{18\mu_f} \quad (45)$$

τ_p can be interpreted as the time necessary to accelerate the particle to a certain fluid velocity via drag force. Therefore, Δt_{DEM} should be smaller than this time. In our simulations, $\tau_p = 0.026$ s, indicating that the chosen Δt_{DEM} is well below the particle relaxation time.

Similar to Δt_{DEM} , there are different criteria for determining Δt_{CFD} . One criterion is fluid relaxation time, τ_{fluid} . This time is similar to the particle relaxation time and is an indicator of the time necessary to accelerate fluid to a certain particle velocity via drag force [46] and is,

$$\tau_{fluid} = \frac{d_p^2}{18\mu_f} \frac{1 - \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d}{\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d} \quad (46)$$

It can be seen that τ_{fluid} is a function of domain-averaged particle volume fraction in the system. This time imposes the upper bound for the time step of solving Navier–Stokes equations. Thus, the chosen Δt_{CFD} should be smaller than τ_{fluid} . The values of τ_{fluid} for various $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$ values (from the lowest to the highest $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$) are: 3.3×10^{-4} , 1.5×10^{-4} , 9.8×10^{-5} , and 6.9×10^{-5} s. The other criterion is the Courant number, that

also can impose an upper bound for Δt_{CFD} . Using the reported value of Δt_{CFD} in Table 6, the maximum Courant number was below 1.0 in our simulations.

The predicted values of the mean-slip Reynolds numbers, $Re_{slip} = \rho_f d_p \langle u_{slip} \rangle_d / \mu_f$ obtained from the slip velocity in the vertical direction,

$$\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d = \frac{\langle (1 - \alpha_p) u_{fz} \rangle_d - \langle \alpha_p u_{pz} \rangle_d}{1 - \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d} \quad (47)$$

for the CFD-DEM and the TFM simulations are demonstrated in Fig. 11. The time-averaging window of the domain-averaged slip velocity in the CFD-DEM simulations of Radl and Sundaresan [42] was $30\tau'_p$, while in our TFM and CFD-DEM simulations, it was considered to be $43\tau'_p$. The particle characteristic time is $\tau'_p = u_t / |g|$, where the terminal velocity of a single particle is, $u_t = 0.232$ m s⁻¹. Note that the averaging process starts once the statistical steady state is established.

As can be deduced from Fig. 11, our CFD-DEM simulations agree well with the results of Radl and Sundaresan [42]. However, there are minor discrepancies between the data, which may be attributed to the differences in numerical implementations of the CFD-DEM solvers, but overall both CFD-DEM results predict a similar trend. The mean-slip Reynolds number is relatively constant at low domain-averaged particle volume fractions, i.e., 0.05 and 0.10, and decreases at higher domain-averaged particle volume fractions, i.e., 0.15 and 0.20. We need to note that, although flow is in statistical steady state, the instantaneous domain-averaged slip velocity fluctuates around its mean value, due to breaking and forming of clusters. Qualitatively, the TFM is in good agreement with our CFD-DEM results and the relative error between our TFM and CFD-DEM simulations for four cases (from the lowest to the highest $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$) are: 12.42, 16.41, 15.57 and 14.13%. The TFM is systematically under-predicting the mean-slip Reynolds number. Bypassing of the fluid flow from the dilute and low particle volume fraction region, increases the domain-averaged slip velocity. Therefore, increasing the size and number of the clusters in the system can lead to larger domain-averaged slip velocity and thus higher mean-slip Reynolds number. However, in larger $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$ values the clusters reach to the maximum packing limit, leading to decrease of the domain-averaged slip velocity, as can be seen in Fig. 11.

The lower values of domain-averaged slip velocity of the TFM in Fig. 11 can be related to the lower degree of clustering compared to the CFD-DEM which is evident from lower value of $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ in the TFM

Fig. 11. Comparison of mean-slip Reynolds numbers between our CFD-DEM, the TFM, and the CFD-DEM results of Radl and Sundaresan [42] for various domain-averaged particle volume fractions.

simulation compared to the CFD-DEM (cf. Table 9). This is also partially visible in Fig. 12, where the instantaneous particle volume fraction profiles of the CFD-DEM and the TFM at various domain-averaged particle volume fractions are presented. The formation of the smaller clusters in the TFM can be attributed to the higher predicted solids pressure values arising from the particle-particle interactions which are resolved using continuum closures rather than physical models (e.g., soft-sphere in the CFD-DEM). In order to address this issue in the TFM, we exemplarily apply the DML (mc) method on the TFM simulations with $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d = 0.05$ and 0.2. The DML (mc) method will help us to resolve the particle-particle interactions in a small DML region and thus we can examine whether resolving these interactions in a small region of the TFM can improve the TFM predictions in the whole system. It needs to be mentioned that we do not use the DML (mmc) approach here, because the TFM is capable of capturing the physics of the clustering and we are only interested in improving the TFM results.

4.2.2. Dilute unbounded fluidization

In this section, we apply the DML (mc) approach to the case of unbounded fluidization with $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d = 0.05$. Fig. 13a shows the location of the DML region. We have chosen a DML region in the middle of the simulation domain to investigate the impact of the DML (mc) approach on the TFM simulation. There are two overlapping boundaries, one is at the top at $z = 0.020$ m and the other one is located at the bottom at $z = 0.012$ m. The insertion regions at the top and bottom each consist of one cell layer, at $z = 0.020 - 0.01975$ m and $z = 0.012 - 0.01225$ m. In this particular case, the particle velocity controller region comprises two cell layers, starting from $z = 0.020$ to $z = 0.0195$ in the top section and from $z = 0.012$ to $z = 0.0125$ in the bottom section, where the particle velocity controller regions include the insertion regions as well. The relaxation regions are made up of two cell layers at the top ($z = 0.0195 - 0.019$ m) and at the bottom ($z = 0.0125 - 0.013$ m). Note

that in these simulations we vary the number of particle velocity controller cell layers from zero to four to study the impact of the controller region width. In case of having four cell layers of the particle velocity controller region the relaxation region is omitted. Finally, the two-way coupling region including twenty four cell layers, stretches from $z = 0.013$ m to $z = 0.019$ m, which covers 18.75% of the total volume of the system.

It can be seen that the DML region in case of unbounded fluidization simulations contains overlapping boundaries, controller, and relaxation regions at the top and bottom. This configuration differs from that of the particle jet simulation (cf. Fig. 5a) and is owed to the fact that in the unbounded fluidization system particle clusters can move both upwards and downwards, while in the particle jets simulations the particle flow is only upwards. Therefore, the criterion to determine the location of each section in the DML region is the direction of particle flow.

In these simulations, the two-way coupling between the TFM and the CFD-DEM in the DML region starts after the underlying TFM simulation reaches to a statistically steady state. The instantaneous snapshot of the DML (mc) approach in Fig. 13b, shows the particle volume fraction field of the TFM overlaid with the discrete particles. The preferential concentration of the discrete particles with the fluid flow which leads to clustering can be seen, as well.

To quantitatively compare the predictions of the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc), we evaluate the mean and standard deviation values of $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$, $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$, $\langle \mathbf{k}_p \rangle_d$, and $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain with a time-averaging window of $43\tau_p'$ and list the results in Table 7–10.

The accuracy of the DML simulations depends on the number of particle velocity controller cell layers. For specifying the minimum number of particle velocity cell layers, we propose to use particle velocity cell layers larger than the size of smallest heterogeneous structures (particle clusters). The characteristic length scale, \mathbb{L}_{ch} , of the smallest particle cluster can be obtained using,

Fig. 12. Instantaneous particle volume fraction profiles for various domain-averaged particle volume fractions obtained from the CFD-DEM (top row) and the TFM (bottom row) simulations.

Fig. 13. (a) Schematic of the discrete magnification lens region, (b) Instantaneous snapshot of the DML (mc) simulation with discrete particles.

Table 7

Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$ in the DML region between the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches. The acronym #PVCCL stands for the number of particle velocity controller cell layers.

Approach	#PVCCL	Mean Val.	St. Dev.
CFD-DEM	–	0.050	0.0058
TFM	–	0.050	0.0072
DML (mc)	–	0.048	0.0052
DML (mc)	2	0.050	0.0070
DML (mc)	3	0.050	0.0080
DML (mc)	4	0.050	0.0067

$$\mathbb{L}_{ch} = \frac{u_t^2}{g Fr^{-2/3}} \quad (48)$$

where $Fr = u_t^2 / g d_p$ denotes the particle-based Froude number. For the used particles in our simulations of unbounded fluidization, $\mathbb{L}_{ch} = 4.18 d_p$, which is larger than one mesh cell layer. Therefore, utilizing

Table 8

Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain between the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches in case of dilute unbounded fluidization. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the mean value of the CFD-DEM. The acronym #PVCCL stands for the number of particle velocity controller cell layers.

Approach	#PVCCL	DML region			Full domain		
		Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.	Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.
CFD-DEM	–	0.3135	0.0276	–	0.3123	0.0193	–
TFM	–	0.2744	0.0247	12.47	0.2735	0.0164	12.42
DML (mc)	2	0.2881	0.0267	8.10	0.2826	0.0154	9.51
DML (mc)	3	0.2950	0.0265	5.90	0.2902	0.0191	7.08
DML (mc)	4	0.2989	0.0372	4.66	0.2934	0.0284	6.05

Table 9

Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain between the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches in case of dilute unbounded fluidization. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the mean value of the CFD-DEM. The acronym #PVCCL stands for the number of particle velocity controller cell layers.

Approach	#PVCCL	DML region			Full domain		
		Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.	Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.
CFD-DEM	–	0.0022	0.0005	–	0.0023	0.0002	–
TFM	–	0.0013	0.0004	43.47	0.0014	0.0001	39.13
DML (mc)	2	0.0015	0.0007	30.43	0.0016	0.0001	30.43
DML (mc)	3	0.0016	0.0005	27.27	0.0017	0.0001	26.09
DML (mc)	4	0.0018	0.0006	18.18	0.0017	0.0002	26.09

more than one mesh cell layers as the particle controller cell layers will be an optimal choice.

It is important to confirm that the DML (mc) approach with different number of particle velocity controller cell layers is mass conservative. In other words, the inflow and outflow mass of the discrete particles from the boundaries of the DML region is corresponding to the ones from the underlying TFM simulation. To do so, $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$ values from different simulations in the DML region are reported in Table 7. Note that since the unbounded fluidization simulations are statistically steady, the time-averaged value of $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$ in the DML region should be equal to the $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$ of the whole system, which is equal to 0.05. It can be deduced from Table 7 that the mean values of $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$ predicted from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approach with particle velocity controller is equal to 0.05. However, the mean value of the DML (mc) approach without the particle velocity controller is 0.048, suggesting that the simulation was not conserving mass and discrete particles were exiting the DML region too quickly. This underlines the efficacy and significance

Table 10

Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle k_p \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain between the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches in case of dilute unbounded fluidization. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the mean value of the CFD-DEM. The acronym #PVCCL stands for the number of particle velocity controller cell layers.

Approach	#PVCCL	DML region			Full domain		
		Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.	Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.
CFD-DEM	–	0.0170	0.0041	–	0.0174	0.0034	–
TFM	–	0.0121	0.0030	28.82	0.0130	0.0022	25.29
DML (mc)	2	0.0144	0.0038	15.29	0.0139	0.0026	20.11
DML (mc)	3	0.0159	0.0043	6.47	0.0155	0.0035	10.92
DML (mc)	4	0.0148	0.0042	12.94	0.0156	0.0037	10.34

of utilizing the particle velocity controller in the DML simulations. Since the DML (mc) simulation without particle velocity controller is not conserving the mass, we will not report its results in the following.

As can be seen in Table 8, the value of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain obtained from the TFM is respectively, 12.47% and 12.42% lower compared to the CFD-DEM. This can be attributed to the lower degree of clustering in the TFM simulation, which is measured by $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ as listed in Table 9. The value of $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain obtained from the TFM simulation is respectively, 43.47% and 39.13% lower than the one predicted from the CFD-DEM. Moreover, the TFM predicts lower $\langle k_p \rangle_d$ than the CFD-DEM in the DML region and full domain as listed in Table 10. Thus, it is of great interest to investigate the effect of applying the DML (mc) approach on the TFM predictions.

The results presented in Table 8–10 indicate that applying the DML (mc) approach indeed improves the TFM results in the DML region. However, depending on the number of particle velocity controller cell layers, the accuracy of the DML (mc) approach varies. It can be concluded from Table 8 that utilizing two, three and four layers of particle velocity controller cells, the relative error between the CFD-DEM and the TFM in terms of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$ in the DML region, decreases from 12.47% to 8.10, 5.90, and 4.66%, respectively. Moreover, Table 9 exhibits that the relative error of the TFM in terms of $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ in the DML region, reduces from 43.47% respectively to 30.43, 27.27, and 18.18%. Finally, the relative error of the TFM in terms of $\langle k_p \rangle_d$ in the DML region drops from 28.82% to 15.29, 6.47, and 12.94%, respectively (see Table 10).

Based on the observations it can be deduced that in this unbounded fluidization case, the optimal choice of the number of particle velocity controller cell layers is four, implying that there is no need for the relaxation region to gain the most accurate results.

To evaluate the impact of the DML (mc) simulations on the properties of the full simulation domain, the comparison between the mean and standard deviation values of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$, $\langle k_p \rangle_d$, and $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) simulations is presented in Tables 8–10.

The results are demonstrating similar trends as the results in the DML region. The relative error of the TFM compared to the CFD-DEM data in terms of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$, reduces from 12.42% to 9.51, 7.08, and 6.05% using two, three, and four particle velocity controller cell layers, respectively (see Table 8). The relative error values of the TFM in terms of $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ presented in Table 9, show a decrease of the relative error from 39.13% to 30.43, 26.09, and 26.09%, respectively. At last, the relative error values of $\langle k_p \rangle_d$ listed in Table 10, reveal an error reduction from 25.29%, to 20.11, 10.92, and 10.34%, respectively.

As can be inferred from the results, in the DML region the influence of the DML (mc) approach is more significant than the full domain. This is traced to the small size of the DML region compared to the full domain, thus improving the results of the DML (mc) approach in the full domain scale would require choosing a larger DML region. However, it

should be considered that the goal of the DML approaches is to affect the TFM simulation in a small region.

4.2.3. Dense unbounded fluidization

We extend the application of the DML (mc) approach to dense unbounded fluidization case with $\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d = 0.20$. Similar to the dilute case we apply the DML (mc) method using four particle velocity controller cell layers, in the same location of the system as shown in Fig. 13.

As Table 11 shows, the predicted values of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$ from the TFM in the DML region and full domain are 17.63% and 14.13% lower than the CFD-DEM results, respectively. However, applying the DML (mc) with four particle velocity controller cell layers, can alleviate the error between the TFM and the CFD-DEM and decrease it to 0.59% in the DML region and to 5.95% in the full domain.

Evaluating $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ reveals that the TFM predictions are 25.10% and 25.13% lower than the ones obtained from the CFD-DEM simulations in the DML region and full domain, respectively (cf. Table 12). Adopting the DML (mc) approach can reduce the error of the TFM to 2.02% and 17.77% in the DML region and full domain, respectively.

It can be note from Table 13 that applying the DML (mc) can decrease the relative error of the TFM compared to the CFD-DEM in terms of $\langle k_p \rangle_d$ from 26.62% to 18.18% in the DML region and in full domain, from 29.55% to 19.87%.

Similar to our observation in the dilute unbounded fluidization case, it can be deduced from these results that the influence of the DML (mc) approach is more pronounced in the DML region than in the full domain. Therefore, it is best to utilize the DML (mc) approach in areas where the TFM simulation is not able to produce results with the desired accuracy.

4.2.4. Numerical costs

The numerical costs related to the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) simulations of the dilute and the dense unbounded fluidization simulations for 1 s of calculations on 32-core CPU of 3.1 GHz frequency are reported in Table 14. As expected the CFD-DEM simulations require extensive computational resources compared to the TFM and the numerical effort increases by increasing the particle volume fraction in the system. The DML (mc) method entails less computational costs than the CFD-DEM, i.e., for dilute and dense cases speed ups of 21.94% and 62.33% can be observed, respectively. However, compared to the TFM, the numerical cost is quite high, due to the reasons mentioned in section 4.1.4. Nevertheless, in denser systems, the computational cost of the DML (mc) approach is significantly lower than the CFD-DEM.

5. Conclusion and outlook

We introduced and successfully implemented a novel hybrid multi-scale modelling method for simulations of fluid-particle systems, referred to “discrete magnification lens” method. The discrete magnification region is nested into a TFM simulation and consists of overlapping boundary, insertion, particle velocity controller, relaxation and two-way coupling regions. The underlying TFM fields in the magnification lens region provide the necessary information such as number of discrete

Table 11

Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain between the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches in case of dense unbounded fluidization. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the mean value of the CFD-DEM. The acronym #PVCCL stands for the number of particle velocity controller cell layers.

Approach	#PVCCL	DML region			Full domain		
		Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.	Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.
CFD-DEM	–	0.2541	0.0525	–	0.2420	0.0418	–
TFM	–	0.2093	0.0274	17.63	0.2078	0.0165	14.13
DML (mc)	4	0.2526	0.0394	0.59	0.2276	0.0207	5.95

Table 12

Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle a_p^2 \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain between the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches in case of dense unbounded fluidization. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the mean value of the CFD-DEM. The acronym #PVCCL stands for the number of particle velocity controller cell layers.

Approach	#PVCCL	DML region			Full domain		
		Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.	Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.
CFD-DEM	–	0.0247	0.0044	–	0.02578	0.0018	–
TFM	–	0.0185	0.0028	25.10	0.0193	0.0011	25.13
DML (mc)	4	0.0242	0.0033	2.02	0.0212	0.0011	17.77

Table 13

Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle k_p \rangle_d$ in the DML region and full domain between the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches in case of dense unbounded fluidization. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the mean value of the CFD-DEM. The acronym #PVCCL stands for the number of particle velocity controller cell layers.

Approach	#PVCCL	DML region			Full domain		
		Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.	Mean val.	St. dev.	% Rel. err.
CFD-DEM	–	0.0154	0.0045	–	0.0176	0.0026	–
TFM	–	0.0113	0.0022	26.62	0.0124	0.0011	29.55
DML (mc)	4	0.0126	0.0029	18.18	0.0141	0.0020	19.87

particles to be inserted at each coupling time step and fluid phase velocity fields to derive the CFD-DEM simulation. In the controller region, an additional force is applied to the discrete particles to minimize the deviation of the mapped discrete particle velocity from the continuum particle velocity obtained from TFM. Finally, in the two-way coupling region the information from the CFD-DEM is used to force TFM to the desired values.

We applied the discrete magnification lens method to different particle jets. In case of dilute jets, it was observed that the CFD-DEM approach can successfully capture the particle trajectory crossing while the TFM failed, due to lack of considering bi-modal particle velocity distribution. However, it was demonstrated that applying discrete magnification lens model with mass and momentum coupling and only momentum coupling can improve the behavior of the TFM to conform to the one observed in the CFD-DEM simulations. The same observation was made in case of moderate particle jets.

Furthermore, we extended the application of the discrete magnification lens model to unbounded fluidization cases, where the interactions between fluid and particle phases exhibit complex behaviors, leading to the formation of particle clusters. We proposed a criterion to determine the minimum number of particle velocity controller cell layers based on the smallest particle cluster length scale. It was shown that adopting the discrete magnification lens model improves the TFM predictions and by increasing the number of particle velocity controller

Table 14

CPU time of the CFD-DEM, the TFM, and the DML (mc) approaches calculated for the dilute and the dense unbounded fluidization cases.

	Dilute			Dense		
	CFD-DEM	TFM	DML (mc)	CFD-DEM	TFM	DML (mc)
	11.94 h	5.95 h	9.32 h	62.01 h	9.32 h	23.36 h

cell layers the accuracy of the results increases. In addition, the computational time of the discrete magnification lens simulations was lower than the CFD-DEM simulations.

The proposed two-way coupling strategies solely consider the coupling between the mass and/or momentum equations while the coupling between granular temperature values has not been considered. We have assumed that since the semi-implicit source term added to the continuum particle momentum equation is driving the solution of the TFM towards the one obtained from the CFD-DEM, the continuum particle stresses are indirectly closed using the information of the particle velocity field from the CFD-DEM. Moreover, calculating the granular temperature on the fly of CFD-DEM simulations will introduce extra overhead on the computations. Therefore, future studies will need to focus on the effect of coupling granular temperature in the two-way coupling region and the application of the discrete magnification lens method to processes that may benefit from the concept such as fluidized bed with insets. Furthermore, the extension of the discrete magnification lens towards considering non-isothermal, reacting, and poly-disperse flows can be subject of future endeavors. For instance, in the TFM simulations of fluidized beds with inserted heat exchanger tubes, the discrete magnification lens region can be applied around the tube, in this way the tube-to-particle heat transfer can be captured more accurately through discrete particles. If the TFM simulation solves momentum, energy and reaction equations, the discrete magnification lens can be useful to correct the TFM predictions in regions of interest with considering particle surface reactions. To be able to consider poly-disperse flows, the TFM could be modified to consider multiple solid phases (Eulerian multi-fluid approach), if the information from different particle sizes are available in the simulations, the discrete magnification lens method can consider poly-dispersity in the CFD-DEM simulations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Behrad Esgandari: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Daniel Queteschner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Conceptualization. **Stefan Pirker:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Simon Schneiderbauer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955661 (TUSAIL ITN, www.tusail.eu). The authors would like to acknowledge the valuable discussions with Professor J.T. Padding (Delft University of Technology). The last author acknowledges the funding support of the K1-MET GmbH metallurgical competence center. The research program of the K1-MET competence center is supported by COMET (Competence Center for Excellent Technologies), the Austrian program for competence centers. COMET is funded by the Federal Ministry for Transport, Innovation and Technology, the Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs, and the provinces of Upper Austria, Tyrol, and Styria. In addition to the public funding from COMET, this research project is partially financed by the industrial partner Primetals Technologies Austria GmbH.

References

- [1] S. Subramaniam, S. Balachandar, Modeling Approaches and Computational Methods for Particle-Laden Turbulent Flows, Academic Press, 2023, pp. 1–42, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-32-390133-8.00009-8>.
- [2] M.A. van der Hoef, M. van Sint Annaland, N. Deen, J. Kuipers, Numerical simulation of dense gas-solid fluidized beds: a multiscale modeling strategy, *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.* 40 (2008) 47–70, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fluid.40.111406.102130>.
- [3] Y. Tang, J. Kuipers, Multiscale modeling of gas-fluidized beds, in: Modeling Approaches and Computational Methods for Particle-Laden Turbulent Flows, Academic Press, 2023, pp. 483–536, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-32-390133-8.00022-0>.
- [4] Y. Tang, E. Peters, J. Kuipers, S. Kriebitzsch, M.A. van der Hoef, A new drag correlation from fully resolved simulations of flow past monodisperse static arrays of spheres, *AICHE J.* 61 (2) (2015) 688–698, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.14645>.
- [5] M. Mehrabadi, E. Murphy, S. Subramaniam, Development of a gas-solid drag law for clustered particles using particle-resolved direct numerical simulation, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 152 (2016) 199–212, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2016.06.006>.
- [6] M. Khaloufi, J. Capecelatro, Drag force of compressible flows past random arrays of spheres, *Int. J. Multiphase Flow* 165 (2023) 104496, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2023.104496>.
- [7] B. Kravets, T. Rosemann, S. Reinecke, H. Kruggel-Emden, A new drag force and heat transfer correlation derived from direct numerical LBM-simulations of flow through particle packings, *Powder Technol.* 345 (2019) 438–456, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2019.01.028>.
- [8] H. Miao, H. Zhang, Y. Wu, Y. Wang, X. An, PR-DNS investigation on momentum and heat transfer of two interactive non-spherical particles in a fluid, *Powder Technol.* 427 (2023) 118791, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2023.118791>.
- [9] P.A. Cundall, O.D. Strack, A discrete numerical model for granular assemblies, *Géotechnique* 29 (1) (1979) 47–65, <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1979.29.1.47>.
- [10] B. Hoomans, J. Kuipers, W.J. Briels, W.P.M. van Swaaij, Discrete particle simulation of bubble and slug formation in a two-dimensional gas-fluidized bed: a hard-sphere approach, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 51 (1) (1996) 99–118, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2509\(95\)00271-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2509(95)00271-5).
- [11] X. Gao, J. Yu, L. Lu, C. Li, W.A. Rogers, Development and validation of SuperDEM-CFD coupled model for simulating non-spherical particles hydrodynamics in fluidized beds, *Chem. Eng. J.* 420 (2021) 127654, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2020.127654>.
- [12] S. Schneiderbauer, *Continuum Modeling of Gas-Particle Flows: An Overview*, Submitted to *Acta Mechanica*, 2024.
- [13] Y. Igci, S. Sundaresan, Constitutive models for filtered two-fluid models of fluidized gas-particle flows, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 50 (23) (2011) 13190–13201, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie200190q>.
- [14] S. Schneiderbauer, A spatially-averaged two-fluid model for dense large-scale gas-solid flows, *AICHE J.* 63 (8) (2017) 3544–3562, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.15684>.
- [15] W. Bian, X. Chen, J. Wang, A critical comparison of two-fluid model, discrete particle method and direct numerical simulation for modeling dense gas-solid flow of rough spheres, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 210 (2019) 115233, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2019.115233>.
- [16] P. Ostermeier, S. DeYoung, A. Vandersickel, S. Gleis, H. Spliethoff, Comprehensive investigation and comparison of TFM, DenseDPM and CFD-DEM for dense fluidized beds, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 196 (2019) 291–309, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2018.11.007>.
- [17] C. Moliner, F. Marchelli, N. Spanachi, A. Martinez-Felipe, B. Bosio, E. Arato, CFD simulation of a spouted bed: comparison between the discrete element method (DEM) and the two fluid model (TFM), *Chem. Eng. J.* 377 (2019) 120466, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2018.11.164>.
- [18] S. Golshan, B. Esgandari, R. Zarghami, CFD-DEM and TFM simulations of spouted bed, *Chem. Eng. Trans.* 57 (2017) 1249–1254, <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1757209>.
- [19] B. Esgandari, S. Rauchenzauner, C. Goniva, P. Kieckhefer, S. Schneiderbauer, A comprehensive comparison of two-fluid model, discrete element method and experiments for the simulation of single-and multiple-spout fluidized beds, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 267 (2023) 118357, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2022.118357>.
- [20] N. Almohammed, F. Alobaid, M. Breuer, B. Epple, A comparative study on the influence of the gas flow rate on the hydrodynamics of a gas-solid spouted fluidized bed using Euler–Euler and Euler–Lagrange/DEM models, *Powder Technol.* 264 (2014) 343–364, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2014.05.024>.
- [21] Y. Zhang, Q. Chang, W. Ge, Coupling DPM with DNS for dynamic interphase force evaluation, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 231 (2021) 116238, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2020.116238>.
- [22] S. Pirker, D. Kahrmanovic, G. Aichinger, Modeling mass loading effects in industrial cyclones by a combined eulerian–lagrangian approach, *Acta Mech.* 204 (3) (2009) 203–216, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00707-008-0086-7>.
- [23] S. Schneiderbauer, S. Pirker, S. Putteringer, P. Aguayo, V. Touloupidis, A.M. Joaristi, A Lagrangian-Eulerian hybrid model for the simulation of poly-disperse fluidized beds: application to industrial-scale olefin polymerization, *Powder Technol.* 316 (2017) 697–710, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2016.12.063>.
- [24] X. Chen, J. Wang, J. Li, Multiscale modeling of rapid granular flow with a hybrid discrete-continuum method, *Powder Technol.* 304 (2016) 177–185, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2016.08.017>.
- [25] A. Di Renzo, E.S. Napolitano, F.P. Di Maio, Coarse-grain dem modelling in fluidized bed simulation: a review, *Processes* 9 (2) (2021) 279, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9020279>.
- [26] C. Bierwisch, T. Kraft, H. Riedel, M. Moseler, Three-dimensional discrete element models for the granular statics and dynamics of powders in cavity filling, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 57 (1) (2009) 10–31, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmps.2008.10.006>.
- [27] V. Brandt, J. Grabowski, N. Jurtz, M. Kraume, H. Kruggel-Emden, DEM and DEM-CFD modeling of systems with geometric constrictions using a new particle location based multi-level coarse graining approach, *Powder Technol.* 436 (2024) 119447, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2024.119447>.
- [28] S. Pirker, D. Kahrmanovic, C. Kloss, B. Popoff, M. Braun, Simulating coarse particle conveying by a set of Eulerian, Lagrangian and hybrid particle models, *Powder Technol.* 204 (2–3) (2010) 203–213, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2010.07.033>.
- [29] D. Schellander, S. Schneiderbauer, S. Pirker, Numerical study of dilute and dense poly-dispersed gas-solid two-phase flows using an Eulerian and Lagrangian hybrid model, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 95 (2013) 107–118, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2013.03.037>.
- [30] Q. Wang, Y. Feng, J. Lu, W. Yin, H. Yang, P.J. Witt, M. Zhang, Numerical study of particle segregation in a coal beneficiation fluidized bed by a TFM-DEM hybrid model: influence of coal particle size and density, *Chem. Eng. J.* 260 (2015) 240–257, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2014.08.052>.
- [31] W. Yin, S. Wang, K. Zhang, Y. He, Investigation of oxygen-enriched biomass gasification with TFM-DEM hybrid model, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 211 (2020) 115293, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2019.115293>.
- [32] S. Schneiderbauer, M.F. Haider, F. Hauenberger, S. Pirker, A Lagrangian-Eulerian hybrid model for the simulation of industrial-scale gas-solid cyclones, *Powder Technol.* 304 (2016) 229–240, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2016.07.064>.
- [33] X. Chen, J. Wang, Hybrid discrete-continuum model for granular flow, *Proc. Eng.* 102 (2015) 661–667, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.01.160>.
- [34] X. Chen, J. Wang, Dynamic multiscale method for gas-solid flow via spatiotemporal coupling of two-fluid model and discrete particle model, *AICHE J.* 63 (9) (2017) 3681–3691, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.15723>.
- [35] X. Chen, J. Wang, Mesoscale-structure-based dynamic multiscale method for gas-solid flow, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 192 (2018) 864–881, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2018.08.019>.
- [36] K. Agrawal, P.N. Loezos, M. Syamlal, S. Sundaresan, The role of meso-scale structures in rapid gas-solid flows, *J. Fluid Mech.* 445 (2001) 151–185, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112001005663>.

- [37] M. Ishii, T. Hibiki, *Thermo-Fluid Dynamics of Two-Phase Flow*, Springer Science & Business Media, 2010.
- [38] S. Chialvo, J. Sun, S. Sundaresan, Bridging the rheology of granular flows in three regimes, *Phys. Rev. E* 85 (2) (2012) 021305, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.85.021305>.
- [39] Y. Tsuji, T. Kawaguchi, T. Tanaka, Discrete particle simulation of two-dimensional fluidized bed, *Powder Technol.* 77 (1) (1993) 79–87, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(93\)85010-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(93)85010-7).
- [40] D. Queteschiner, *Discrete Element Method: Adaptive Resolution Simulations of Granular Flows for Large-Scale Systems*, Ph.D. thesis., Johannes Kepler University Linz, 2020.
- [41] J. Tausendschön, J. Kolehmainen, S. Sundaresan, S. Radl, Coarse graining Euler-Lagrange simulations of cohesive particle fluidization, *Powder Technol.* 364 (2020) 167–182, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2020.01.056>.
- [42] S. Radl, S. Sundaresan, A drag model for filtered Euler–Lagrange simulations of clustered gas–particle suspensions, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 117 (2014) 416–425, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2014.07.011>.
- [43] R. Beetstra, M.A. van der Hoef, J. Kuipers, Drag force of intermediate Reynolds number flow past mono-and bidisperse arrays of spheres, *AICHE J.* 53 (2) (2007) 489–501, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.11065>.
- [44] D. Queteschiner, T. Lichtenegger, S. Pirker, S. Schneiderbauer, Multi-level coarse-grain model of the DEM, *Powder Technol.* 338 (2018) 614–624, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2018.07.033>.
- [45] M. Uhlmann, An immersed boundary method with direct forcing for the simulation of particulate flows, *J. Comput. Phys.* 209 (2) (2005) 448–476, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2005.03.017>.
- [46] S. Radl, B.C. Gonzales, C. Goniva, S. Pirker, *State of the art in mapping schemes for dilute and dense Euler-Lagrange simulations*, in: *Selected Papers from 10th International Conference on Computational Fluid Dynamics in the oil & gas, Metallurgical and Process Industries*, SINTEF Academic Press, 2015.
- [47] C. Goniva, C. Kloss, N.G. Deen, J.A. Kuipers, S. Pirker, Influence of rolling friction on single spout fluidized bed simulation, *Particuology* 10 (5) (2012) 582–591, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2012.05.002>.
- [48] C.M. Rhie, W.-L. Chow, Numerical study of the turbulent flow past an airfoil with trailing edge separation, *AIAA J.* 21 (11) (1983) 1525–1532, <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.8284>.
- [49] Z. Tacconi, *Feasibility Analysis of a Two-Fluid Solver for Cavitation and Interface Capturing as Implemented in OpenFOAM*, Master's thesis., Politecnico di Milano, 2018.
- [50] C.J. Greenshields, H.G. Weller, *Notes on Computational Fluid Dynamics: General Principles*, CFD Direct Ltd, Reading, UK, 2022.
- [51] O. Desjardins, R.O. Fox, P. Villedieu, A quadrature-based moment method for dilute fluid-particle flows, *J. Comput. Phys.* 227 (4) (2008) 2514–2539, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2007.10.026>.
- [52] S. Cloete, S.T. Johansen, S. Amini, Performance evaluation of a complete Lagrangian KTGF approach for dilute granular flow modelling, *Powder Technol.* 226 (2012) 43–52, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2012.04.010>.
- [53] X. Chen, J. Wang, A comparison of two-fluid model, dense discrete particle model and CFD-DEM method for modeling impinging gas–solid flows, *Powder Technol.* 254 (2014) 94–102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2013.12.056>.
- [54] W.D. Fullmer, C.M. Hrenya, Quantitative assessment of fine-grid kinetic-theory-based predictions of mean-slip in unbounded fluidization, *AICHE J.* 62 (1) (2016) 11–17, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.15052>.
- [55] S. Schneiderbauer, M. Saeedipour, Approximate deconvolution model for the simulation of turbulent gas-solid flows: An a priori analysis, *Phys. Fluids* 30 (2) (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5017004>.
- [56] S. Rauchenzauner, S. Schneiderbauer, Validation study of a spatially-averaged two-fluid model for heat transport in gas-particle flows, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 198 (2022) 123382, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2022.123382>.
- [57] C.M. Hrenya, J.L. Sinclair, Effects of particle-phase turbulence in gas-solid flows, *AICHE J.* 43 (4) (1997) 853–869, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.690430402>.
- [58] C.K. Lun, S.B. Savage, D. Jeffrey, N. Chepur, Kinetic theories for granular flow: inelastic particles in Couette flow and slightly inelastic particles in a general flowfield, *J. Fluid Mech.* 140 (1984) 223–256, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112084000586>.
- [59] Y. Li, Y. Xu, C. Thornton, A comparison of discrete element simulations and experiments for 'sandpiles' composed of spherical particles, *Powder Technol.* 160 (3) (2005) 219–228, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2005.09.002>.
- [60] K. Washino, E.L. Chan, K. Miyazaki, T. Tsuji, T. Tanaka, Time step criteria in DEM simulation of wet particles in viscosity dominant systems, *Powder Technol.* 302 (2016) 100–107, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2016.08.018>.